

THE EFFECT OF THE BONDING BETWEEN THE HPPE FIBER AND THE MATRIX ON THE PROPERTIES AND THE FRACTURE MODE OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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1 Introduction

Application of fiber-reinforced polymer composites (CMs) with a large amount of continuous fiber may be very rewarding because such CMs are high strength low-density materials. The multifilament fiber (a single bundle of filaments) is widely used for reinforcing polymer CMs. Such fiber can consist of several thousand small diametered filaments. The smaller the diameter of the filament is the stronger the fiber. The stronger the fiber is the stronger of the CM may be obtained. With the reduction of filament diameter the fiber/matrix interface grows. It is becoming one of the main structural components of advanced CM.

A lot of studies deal with the multifilament high performance polyethylene (HPPE) fibers such as Dyneema® or Spectra®. Due to nanocrystalline structure of the filaments the advantages of HPPE fibers are low density (0.97 g/cm³), high strength (~4 GPa) high modulus (~120 GPa), excellent ductility and superior resistance to impact, wear, moisture and chemical agents [1]. The high specific properties of HPPE fiber make it possible to produce advanced CMs that combine good mechanical properties with low mass. However, HPPE fibers have weaknesses such as poor adhesion to the resin matrices poor compressive strength, low creep resistance et al. Ward I.M. and co-investigators did significant achievements in the surface modification of HPPE fibers by plasma treatment [1].

In our study a concept of physical and chemical stages of interaction between the matrix and reinforcing fibers during the producing of CMs is discussed [2, 3]. The interaction may be divided into two stages in every elementary part of the fiber/matrix interface: 1) the physical interaction when joining matters generate a physical contact and 2) the chemical interaction which occurs only if at

least one of contacting surfaces has the energy sufficient for the chemical interaction. In case contacting surfaces have low energies, the interaction stops at the stage of forming the physical contact. The strong joint between the fiber and matrix occurs at the stage of the chemical interaction that is characterised by a certain activation energy value. The activation energy of chemical interaction for HPPE fibers is estimated [2]. Based on these estimates, conditions for fibers activations with low-temperature plasma at reduced pressures are found. Using plasma-activated HPPE fibers for reinforcing an epoxy matrix allows one to produce light-weight CMs with high properties. To widely regulate the properties of such CMs it is necessary to control the interaction at the interface [3].

The goal of our work was to study the effect of the fiber/matrix interface on the properties and failure mode of the CM. The facility of the decision was non-equilibrium low-temperature plasma treatment of the fibers.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

As reinforcement, we used Dyneema® SK-75 HPPE fiber from DSM. The SK-75 fiber has a tensile strength of 3.4 GPa, an elastic modulus of 110 GPa, a density of 0.97 g/cm³, an elongation at break of 3.8%. There are 1150 filaments in a single bundle of filaments. The matrix was an epoxy resin Epicot-828 from Shell Chemical Co. cured with polyethylene polyamine. To control the interaction we used plasma treatment of the fiber. The CM specimens were obtained by winding of the fibers on a mandrel.

2.2 Plasma treatment

The fiber was activated by non-equilibrium low-temperature argon high-frequency (RF) plasma at

the reduced pressure from 1.33 up to 660 Pa. The thermal component of such plasma is reduced to a minimum, due to the low density of ion current $j_i = 0.5 - 1 \text{ A/m}^2$ and small duration of plasma influence on the fiber.

2.3 Measurements of CM mechanical properties

Tensile and shear properties of CMs were compared with that of composites reinforced with untreated fibers. The strength of the CMs in tension was determined on an Instron 3382 universal testing machine at a cross-head speed of 5 and 10 mm/min in the range of loads from 0 to 5 t by rigid half-disks (NOL-Ring method standardized in the USA: ASTM D 2291-67). The shear strength of the CMs was measured using three-point bending tests. The samples were about 35 mm in length and 3 mm in thickness, and 10 mm in width.

3 Results and discussion

Obtaining a CM begins with impregnation of a solid reinforcing fiber by a liquid matrix. As a result of moisture, a region of physical contact of the fiber with the matrix is formed. Their further interaction occurs exactly on this interface; this interaction continues even after solidification of the matrix.

Possible chemical interaction of the CM components increases the joint strength of the fiber with the matrix, which also affects the properties of the CM.

Chemical interaction begins on the active centres of the reinforcing fiber. Activation of the fiber by special plasma treatment makes it possible to stimulate its ability to interact with the matrix and a result to change the properties of the CM.

In the initial state HPPE fiber is chemically inert, it has low surface energy ($\sim 33 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$), and it badly combines with a matrix of polymer materials. It leads to the splitting of such CM.

Activation by plasma increases the surface energy of the fiber; this is displayed in an increase in the height of capillarity of the liquid matrix by the fiber and in an increase in the joint strength by 2 – 3 times [3]. Owing to increased area of the fiber/matrix interface, the mechanical properties of such CM also increase. The increase in the joint strength of the fiber to the matrix is also displayed in the nature of the failure mode of the CM.

Typical stress-strain curves for CMs reinforced with the HPPE fiber are shown in Fig. 1. The splitting

was observed under the longitudinal tension of CM reinforced with untreated fiber. Due to this splitting small fluctuations were produced in the load P on the stress-strain curve (Fig. 1, curve 1). This kind of interface structure cannot transfer stress effectively; it causes poor adhesion.

Fig. 1. Stress - strain curves of CMs reinforced with initial (1) and plasma-activated (2) HPPE fibers.

Plasma treatment of HPPE fiber increases the bonding capacity of the fiber and the matrix. As a result, the properties of the CM are increased (table).

Table: Properties of PE composites

Fiber treatment	V_f , %	σ_t , GPa	τ_{sh} , MPa
Untreated	40-45	0.70-1.1	12
Plasma-treated	43-45	0.89-1.54	19

After the treatment of SK-75 fiber, the composite shear strength (τ_{sh}) increased by the factors of 1.6 (from 12 to 19 MPa).

The plasma treatment of the fiber raised the tensile strength (σ_t) of the CM by 30% and decreased the relative strain by 25 % (Fig. 1, curve 2).

The CM reinforced with plasma-activated fiber breaks as a solid monolithic material. The passing of CM into a monolithic material can be explained by the structural changes of the interface under certain conditions of plasma treatment of the fiber.

The interaction at the interface between the matrix and the fiber passes from physical into chemical interaction. The strong bonds between them are

formed on the chemically active centres of the treated fiber. We observed such chemically active centres with the help of an optical microscope.

Fig. 2 shows a microphotograph of the surface of the filament, which is partially separated from the matrix under CM tension. The chemically active centres of strong bonding of the matrix to the fiber are visible as the white strips coming from the fiber and extending toward the matrix. All strips deviate aside to the action of loading, which is transferred from the matrix to the fiber. This can be explained by the fibrillary-porous structure of the fiber, which intensely scatters light under loading and allows one fixing the redistribution of the load between the matrix and the fiber visually as well as estimating their interaction.

Fig. 2. A microphotograph of chemically active centres on the surface of the filament in the matrix after a tensile test of CM.

HPPE fiber is obtained by multiple extractions from gel of ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) in adsorption-active liquid [1] where the Rebinder's effect is displayed [4]. This effect promotes the appearance of transversal cracks in the fiber (so called crazes). As a result of cracks propagation, unique fibrillary-porous fiber structure is formed.

It can be seen from Fig.2 that precisely the craze walls are the active centres to which white bands appearing on the most loaded regions of the matrix are connected. The distance between the fixing centres constitutes a few microns, which corresponds to the dimensions of the crazing zone and is in good agreement with the data [1, 4].

Conclusion

1. In the CMs reinforced with plasma-activated HPPE fiber chemically active centres are formed on the surface of filaments. The centres provide a strong bonding between the fiber and the matrix. They can be observed through an optical microscope as the white stripes coming from the filaments to the matrix and bent in the direction of the external load.
2. The opposite walls of transversal cracks (crazes) are the active centres in HPPE fiber.
- 3 Plasma activation of HPPE fiber increases the joint strength of the fiber to the matrix and, correspondingly, the strength of the CM on the whole. After RF-plasma treatment of Dyneema® SK-75 fiber the composite tensile strength increased by 30%.
4. The failure mode of composites reinforced with plasma-activated HPPE fibers points to a high strength of the bond between the fibers and matrix.

References

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